

Generation and Reactions of Inorganic Radicals with Special Reference to Carbonate Radicals

T. P. ELANGO, V. RAMAKRISHNAN and J. C. KURIACOSE*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600 036

Methods of generation of a few inorganic radicals by irradiation are briefly reviewed and their properties discussed. The carbonate radical is dealt with in some detail. Its modes of reaction with several types of organic substrates, such as aromatic amines, aliphatic open chain amines and cyclic amines with bridgehead nitrogen atoms are discussed. Carbonate radical forms an adduct with anilines *via* electrophilic attack, the data suggesting that an *ipso* carbon attack is the initial step. The adduct dissociates into ArNH_2^+ (cation) and $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ giving rise to the photoproducts. Aliphatic amines react by a dual mechanism, *viz.* (i) hydrogen abstraction and (ii) electron transfer. Tertiary amines react *via* electron transfer. Primary and secondary amines react probably by hydrogen abstraction. Cyclic amines with bridgehead nitrogen atoms display widely different reactivities. These differences are explained in terms of 'Through Bond Resonance' concept of Hoffmann.

FREE radicals are highly reactive and have been implicated as the active intermediates in a variety of chemical and biochemical reactions. They initiate several types of reactions, like (i) oxidation/reduction reactions, (ii) radical dimerisation and induced polymerisation, (iii) electron transfer and (iv) addition and substitution reactions. Radicals in general are very short-lived and studies on them require special techniques such as microsecond and nanosecond measurement devices. In recent years picosecond techniques have also been used. The experimental devices consist of three components, (i) a means to generate the radicals, like a photolysis flash source, a laser source or an ionising pulse (pulse radiolysis), (ii) a reaction cell and (iii) a detection and measuring unit: to determine the concentration of the radicals at different time intervals.

While there is much literature on organic free radicals, work on inorganic radicals has not been exhaustive. In recent years, OH^\cdot , $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ and $\text{PO}_4^{\cdot-}$ are some of the inorganic radicals that have received some attention. When aqueous solutions are irradiated with powerful ionising radiations, solvated electrons and OH^\cdot radicals are invariably produced. These, in turn, produce other radicals through secondary reactions. This review deals with the work on carbonate radicals. The choice of carbonate radical for extensive coverage has been dictated by the fact that most of the work of the authors has been on this system. A brief summary of data regarding other radicals is also given. A complete bibliography of references dealing with almost all inorganic radicals is available in an excellent monograph by Neta¹.

Hydroxyl radical is invariably formed in many reactions in aqueous medium and it is the precursor

of most radicals. This radical oxidises several inorganic ions producing inorganic radicals. Excellent report on this radical are available² and here it is useful to list the types of reactions undergone by this radical.

Addition reaction

Hydrogen abstraction

Dimerisation

Electron transfer

Oxidation

Sulphate radical ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$):

This radical can be generated by thermal methods³, photochemical methods⁴ and pulse radiolysis⁵.

It absorbs maximally at λ_{max} 450 nm, ϵ_{max} 1 100. Like the hydroxyl radical, it is a versatile species capable of entering into a variety of reactions. Examples of reactions are

Oxidation

Addition

Oxidative decarboxylation

Hydrogen abstraction

$\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ reacts with several anions, such as Cl^- , CO_3^{2-} to yield the radicals as a result of one-electron oxidation. With benzene derivatives oxidation takes place. For a more extensive list one should refer to the monograph by Neta¹. Carbonate radical ($\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$) is similar to $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radical in several respects but $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ is less reactive than $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radical.

Carbonate radical ($\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ or $\text{CO}_3\dot{\text{H}}$):

This radical is generated by three methods, (i) pulse radiolysis, (ii) photolysis of carbonate-persulphate mixture and (iii) photodecomposition of carbonatoammine complexes of cobalt.

Pulse radiolysis method: Carbonate radicals can be generated by pulse radiolysis of aqueous solutions of carbonate or bicarbonate saturated with N_2O^0 .

Photolysis methods: Flash photolysis of a mixture of persulphate and carbonate generates carbonate radicals

Since sulphate radical is a more powerful oxidising reagent than $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ the above reactions are possible. Carbonate or bicarbonate is taken in large excess and the solution is maintained alkaline^{7,8}. This procedure is not suitable if studies are to be made in acid or neutral media.

Hoffmann *et al.*^{9,10} generated $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot+}$ radical by the flash photolysis of certain carbonatoammine complexes of Co^{III} , like $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]^+$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CO}_3]^+$ *etc.* Irradiation of these solutions with 254 nm sources (low pressure Hg lamp) also

produces the carbonate radical, but in small concentrations. Equation (20) represents the reaction,

During irradiation, ligand to metal charge transfer band excitation takes place. The singlet CT state inter-system crosses to triplet CT state which eventually dissociates to yield Co^{2+} and $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$, *etc.* This method is excellently suited for investigations in the pH range 4-11 and consequently uniquely appropriate for investigations under acid/neutral conditions. The acid-base properties of this radical have been well investigated by Hoffmann *et al.*¹⁰.

Spectra of $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ and $\text{CO}_3\text{H}^{\cdot}$ are identical. Carbonate radical is a good oxidising reagent ($E_{\text{red}} = 2.1 \text{ V}$). It can also enter into a variety of reactions and the types of reactions undergone by it are (i) bimolecular self decay, (ii) oxidation, (iii) hydrogen abstraction and (iv) addition.

The following examples are illustrative

Self decay¹¹

Oxidation

e.g., M = triacetoneammine *N*-oxyl radical.

Hydrogen abstraction

Addition

Quite a few workers have measured the rate constants of the reactions involving the carbonate radicals. Mention must be made of the initial works of Hoffmann *et al.*^{12,13}. Reactions with metal ions like Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , *etc.* and with some coordination compounds have also been studied¹⁴.

Kinetic studies:

In the presence of a reactant, S, carbonate radical disappears by two processes which may be competitive.

Self decay

Scavenging

The reaction is followed by observing the decrease of absorbance at 600 nm (λ_{max} of $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$). The overall disappearance of carbonate radical is

given by equation (28).

$$-\frac{d[\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}]^2 + k_2[\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}][\text{S}] \quad (28)$$

k_1 is of the order of $\sim 2 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. If the second term is sufficiently larger than the first term then self decay can be neglected. This is true when $[\text{S}] \gg [\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}]$ and $k_2 \gg k_1$. Further, in cases where $[\text{S}] \gg [\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}]$, the reaction is most likely to follow pseudo-first order kinetics. In these cases the pseudo-first order rate constants are evaluated and k_2 values are obtained therefrom. If the first term on the right hand side of equation (28) is not small compared with the second term then suitable kinetic procedures indicated by Nakamura *et al.*¹⁵ are to be followed. It is therefore possible to determine k_2 whatever may be the situation that prevails.

Since the self decay of carbonate radical (equation 22) proceeds with a rate constant $\sim 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, for any substrate which reacts with this radical with a rate constant 10^8 - $10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the first term can be made negligible. However, in these cases substrate concentration cannot be increased beyond a limit as the reaction may become too fast and may be almost complete within the time resolution of the measuring instrument. With substrates having rate constants 10^4 - $10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, a fairly high concentration of the substrate can be employed.

By virtue of its high and versatile reactivity carbonate radical reacts with almost all organic compounds and a large number of inorganic compounds. It reacts with hydrocarbons, alcohols, amines, sulphur compounds, *etc.* In these cases, the reaction proceeds mostly by electron abstraction or hydrogen abstraction by the radical. The radicals ensuing from the organic substrates undergo chemical transformations characteristic of their thermal reactions. Table 1 gives the rate constants for some typical organic compounds.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS OF SELECTED REACTIONS OF CARBONATE RADICAL WITH ORGANIC SUBSTRATES*

Substrate	k_2 M s	pH
Methanol	5×10^3	12.5
Ethanol	1.5×10^4	12.5
Propan-1-ol	1.9×10^4	12.1 to 12.7
Propan-2-ol	3.9×10^4	12.1 to 12.7
t-Butanol	$< 2.0 \times 10^3$	6.4
Glucose	7.0×10^4	7.0
Glycine	$< 10^3$	7.0
Indole	3.2×10^6	7.0 to 12.0
Benzene	$< 5.0 \times 10^4$	12.0
Anisole	2.8×10^5	—
Phenol	2.2×10^7	7.0
Phenoxide ion	2.4×10^6	12.5
Dimethylaniline	1.8×10^6	7.0

* Data from Ref. 1.

A casual study of the reactivities of various organic substrates reveals the following. (i) Alcohols

react probably *via* loss of hydrogen atom to the carbonate radical. Among the alcohols tertiary alcohols which lack an alpha C-H bond are the most inert. (ii) Amines are relatively more reactive than alcohols because they can act as better electron donors. (iii) With aromatics adduct formation takes place involving electrophilic reaction. Eventually the substrate can also be oxidised. Electron releasing groups render the benzene ring more reactive. Rate constants for substituted benzene compounds can be correlated with the Hammett (σ) constants.

The authors of this paper have made extensive studies on the rate constants of the following types of compounds with $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ radical¹⁶⁻¹⁹, (i) aniline and its derivatives (aromatic amines), (ii) aliphatic amines (open chain amines, cyclic amines with bridgehead nitrogen atoms) and (iii) some inorganic complexes. In most cases, the product has been identified. For the determination of the nature of the product, a cobalt complex (source of $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ radical) plus the organic substrate is irradiated with a continuous source (low pressure Hg lamp, output $\sim 254 \text{ nm}$).

*Reactions with aromatic amines*¹⁷: Aromatic amines react with $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ with high rate constants. For a typical substrate like aniline, the rate constant is $\sim 5 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This value remains more or less the same in a wide range of pH studied (pH 6-11). $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ radical exists as $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ above pH 9 and below this value it exists as $\text{CO}_3\text{H}^{\cdot}$. The results imply that $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ and its protonated form, *viz.* $\text{CO}_3\text{H}^{\cdot}$ react at the same rate with aniline. Table 2 gives the rate constants with a few substituted anilines.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF CARBONATE RADICAL WITH SUBSTITUTED ANILINES*
pH=8.5

Amine	k_2 M s
Aniline	5.0×10^8
p-Chloroaniline	4.3×10^8
p-Bromoaniline	3.8×10^8
p-Aminobenzoic acid	2.0×10^8
p-Nitroaniline	7.3×10^7
p-Fluoroaniline	6.2×10^8
p-Toluidine	9.1×10^8

* Data from Ref. 17.

These rate constants afford a poor log k_2 vs σ correlation with σ_m or σ_p^0 constants for the substituents. The best correlation is obtained for σ_p^+ values of Brown and Okamoto²⁰ with $\rho = -1.0$. This suggests that $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot-}$ attacks the substrate by an electrophilic reaction. This can also imply an electron transfer, but theoretical calculations indicate that in these systems direct electron transfer as the first and foremost step is not possible.

In recent times, a good deal of kinetic studies have been made on thermal reactions of anilines

and dimethylanilines with persulphate. Behrman and Behrman²¹, Sabesan and Venkatasubramanian²², Srinivasan *et al.*²³ and Perumal²⁴ have made efforts to pinpoint the actual atom in the aromatic amine where the first attack by the reagent takes place. Srinivasan *et al.* have observed that for *para*-substituents the best correlation is obtained only with σ_p^+ values and not with other values. This has been taken as a diagnostic criterion of the *ipso* carbon attack (attack on the carbon atom attached to nitrogen).

In the case of reactions of carbonate radical with substituted anilines, the results of such a correlation analysis are as follows. Various types of σ values were plotted against $\log k_2$. σ_p^+ values gave the best straight line suggesting an *ipso* carbon attack. σ_p values also gave a good correlation. But σ_m gave a poor correlation ruling out *ortho* carbon attack. These results suggest that the attack of $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot -}$ radical is on the *ipso* carbon atom. Since the σ_p correlation was also reasonably good, attack on the nitrogen atom can not be totally excluded.

During the flash photolysis a transient absorption attributable to $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2^{\cdot +}$ was observed. This suggests that the adduct yields $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot -}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2^{\cdot +}$. Thus, the electron transfer occurs within the adduct and not between the reactants directly. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2^{\cdot +}$ can further yield $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}^{\cdot}$ leading to several products. In the experiments where aniline and carbonatotetrammincobalt(III) were subjected to continuous irradiation the products obtained were 4-aminodiphenylamine, azobenzene, benzidine and 2-aminodiphenylamine. Scheme 1 explains the mode of reaction of aniline and the formation of the products. The above products were also detected in the photolysis of aniline, but the yields were much less.

Scheme 1. Reaction of aniline with carbonate radical

Reactions with aliphatic amines^{18,19}: A variety of aliphatic amines, open chain amines and cyclic amines with bridgehead nitrogen atoms were studied^{18,19}. These do not behave exactly like anilines, in the sense, that an adduct formation is precluded in these cases. Carbonate radical can react with the aliphatic amines either by an electron transfer mechanism or hydrogen abstraction mechanism. Taking a typical amine, like CH_3NH_2 , N-H bond dissociation energy is far greater than the C-H bond energy. Hence, amines lacking an alpha C-H bond do not react well *via* hydrogen transfer mechanism. An amine, like $\text{RCH}_2\text{NR}'_2$, would yield a Schiff base $\text{RCH}=\text{NR}'_2$. This is the case whether the reaction proceeds by electron transfer or hydrogen transfer (Scheme 2).

(ii) α -Hydrogen abstraction

or

Scheme 2. Mechanisms of reactions of aliphatic amines with carbonate radical.

Table 3 gives the reaction products and Table 4 the kinetic data on aliphatic amines. Both the mechanisms suggest the order of reactivity as tertiary > secondary > primary. The gradient is small and it suggests that all the amines do not react *via* electron transfer. There is evidence to show that the tertiary amines react by electron loss and others by a hydrogen abstraction mechanism.

TABLE 3—PRODUCTS OF REACTION OF CARBONATE RADICAL WITH SOME ALIPHATIC AMINES*

Amine	Major product identified	Method
n-Butylamine	n-Butyraldehyde	GLC and as DNPH ^a derivative
Cyclohexylamine	Cyclohexanone	GLC and as DNPH derivative
Di-n-propylamine	n-Propionaldehyde	GLC and as DNPH derivative
Triethylamine	Acetaldehyde	As DNPH derivative

* Data from Ref. 19.

^a DNPH derivative: 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot -}$ RADICAL WITH ALIPHATIC AMINES*

pH=11.5

Amine	k_2 M s
n-Butylamine	4.0×10^6
Isobutylamine	4.0×10^6
t-Butylamine	5.8×10^6
Isopropylamine	5.0×10^6
Diethylamine	3.8×10^6
Triethylamine	6.4×10^6
1,4-Diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO)	1.7×10^7
Hexamethylenetetramine	1.7×10^6

* Data from Ref. 19.

A plot of $\log k_2$ vs oxidation peak potentials is linear in respect of the tertiary amines. This indicates that the tertiary amines react almost certainly by an electron transfer mechanism. Indeed, in some cases where the ensuing cation radicals are stable the absorptions corresponding to the cation transient were detected.

Cyclic tertiary amines with bridgehead nitrogen atoms are likely to yield stable cation radicals. Three such amines were studied. These are 1,3,6,8-tetraazatricyclo[4.4.1.1.]dodecane (TATCD), DABCO and hexamethylenetetramine (HMT).

One would normally expect all the three of these to exhibit similar reactivities. Surprisingly, TATCD and DABCO have high rate constants, and also produce the corresponding radical cations, namely, TATCD⁺ and DABCO⁺. The absorptions of the transients attributable to these cations were observed. HMT is a thousand times less reactive than the other two, and does not yield HMT⁺. These differences between HMT and the other two cyclic amines are best understood in terms of the 'Through Bond and Through Space Interaction' concept advanced by Hoffmann^{25,26}. Hoffmann introduced this concept to explain certain special properties, such as reactivities and the photoelectron spectra of DABCO, norbornadiene, etc. Full discussion of this concept would certainly be a rewarding exercise, but since this would be outside the scope of this review, only a brief reference is made. In DABCO and TATCD, one can locate two nitrogen atoms although not directly connected by a bond, at a close distance. Because of their proximity the non-bonding orbitals centred on the two nitrogen atoms (n_1 and n_2) can overlap and interact to yield two orbitals of the type $(n_1 + n_2)$ and $(n_1 - n_2)$. In these molecules there is a C-C bond which is parallel to the line joining two nitrogen atoms (viz. $n_1 + n_2$, and $n_1 - n_2$ orbitals). Consequently, there can be further interactions (subject to orbital symmetry considerations) between the nitrogen orbitals and σ_{C-C} and σ_{C-C}^* . These interactions exist only in TATCD and DABCO. In HMT, there is no C-C bond parallel to N-N orbital and hence similar interaction does not exist. The observed differences are due to this factor.

Conclusion :

Many thermal reactions of inorganic ions are mediated by the radicals. While studying the

kinetics of the thermal reactions one gets a composite rate constant. It is not possible to directly measure the rates of the steps where radicals are directly implicated. Any inference regarding these is clouded by a variety of factors. These radicals can be generated by pulse radiolysis or flash photolysis and one can conveniently measure the rates of their reactions. These methods can also go a long way in establishing the mechanisms of photochemical reactions and not infrequently thermal reactions as well.

References

1. A. B. ROSS and P. NETA, "Rate Constants of Inorganic Radicals in Aqueous Solutions", NBS-USA Monographs, NSRDS-NBS-65.
2. L. M. DORFMAN and G. E. ADAMS, "Reactivity of the Hydroxyl Radical in Aqueous Solutions", NBS-USA Monographs, NSRDS-NBS-46.
3. W. K. WILMARTH, N. SCHWARTZ and C. R. GIULIANO, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1983, **51**, 243.
4. L. DOGLIOTTI and E. HAYON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1472.
5. P. NETA, P. MADHAVAN, HAYAZEMEL and R. W. FESSENDEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 163.
6. J. L. WEEKS and J. RABANI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2100.
7. O. P. CHAWLA and R. W. FESSENDEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 2693.
8. V. A. KUZMIN, *High Energy Chem.*, (Engl. Transl.), 1979, **6**, 338.
9. V. W. COPE and M. Z. HOFFMANN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 227.
10. S. N. CHEN, V. W. COPE and M. Z. HOFFMANN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **77**, 1111.
11. J. LILIE, R. J. HANRAHAN and A. HENGLEIN, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **11**, 225.
12. S. N. CHEN and M. Z. HOFFMANN, *Radiat. Res.*, 1973, **56**, 40.
13. S. N. CHEN, M. Z. HOFFMANN and G. H. PARSONS, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1975, **79**, 1911.
14. V. W. COPE, M. Z. HOFFMANN and S. N. CHEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 2665.
15. M. NAKAMURA, O. ITO and M. MATSUDA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1980, **102**, 698.
16. T. P. ELANGO, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, 1984.
17. T. P. ELANGO, V. RAMAKRISHNAN, S. VANCHERAN and J. C. KURIACOSE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Chem. Sci.*, 1984, **93**, 47.
18. T. P. ELANGO, V. RAMAKRISHNAN and J. C. KURIACOSE, Fifth International Conference on Chemical Conversion and Storage of Solar Energy (IPS-5), Osaka, August 1984.
19. T. P. ELANGO, S. VANCHERAN, V. RAMAKRISHNAN and J. C. KURIACOSE, *Tetrahedron*.
20. H. C. BROWN and Y. OKAMATO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 331.
21. E. J. BRERMAN and W. BEHRMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 4551.
22. A. SABESAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 1639.
23. C. SRINIVASAN, S. PERUMAL and N. ARUMUGHAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A* 1980, **19**, 160.
24. S. PERUMAL, Ph.D. Thesis, Madurai-Kamraj University, 1985.
25. R. HOFFMANN, A. IMAMURA and W. J. HEHRE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1499.
26. R. HOFFMANN, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1971, **4**, 1.